

Clinical and Etiological Profile and Outcomes of Children with Status Epilepticus Admitted to a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit: A Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract:

Background: Status epilepticus (SE) is a life-threatening neurological emergency, particularly in children, where prolonged seizures can result in significant morbidity and mortality. Understanding the clinical and etiological profiles of pediatric SE is crucial for improving outcomes.

Aim: To evaluate the clinical presentation, etiological factors, treatment, and outcomes of children with status epilepticus admitted to a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) in a tertiary care hospital.

Methods: This prospective observational study included 80 children aged 1 month to 14 years diagnosed with status epilepticus and admitted to the PICU. Data were collected on demographics, clinical presentation, underlying etiologies, treatments administered, and outcomes. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 5.8 years, with a male-to-female ratio of 1.35:1. The most common type of SE was generalized convulsive, observed in 58.7% of cases. Febrile seizures (32.5%) and CNS infections (25%) were the leading etiological factors. The mortality rate was 7.5%, with CNS infections and structural brain lesions associated with significantly higher mortality ($p < 0.05$). Neurological sequelae occurred in 12.5% of survivors, particularly in those with structural brain lesions.

Conclusion: The study highlights the diverse etiological spectrum of pediatric SE, with febrile seizures being the most common cause. However, CNS infections and structural brain lesions were linked to poorer outcomes, including higher mortality and neurological sequelae. Early identification and aggressive management of high-risk etiologies are essential for improving prognosis.

Recommendations: Based on the findings, it is recommended that healthcare providers prioritize rapid diagnosis and tailored interventions for children presenting with SE, particularly in cases of CNS infections and structural brain lesions. Further research is needed to develop region-specific management protocols and to explore the role of new therapeutic agents in refractory SE.

Keywords: Status Epilepticus, Pediatrics, CNS Infections, Febrile Seizures, Neurological Outcomes.

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Introduction

Status epilepticus (SE) is a neurological emergency characterized by prolonged or repeated seizures without full recovery of consciousness between episodes. It is associated with significant morbidity and mortality, especially in children, where the developing brain is particularly vulnerable to prolonged epileptic activity. SE is defined as a continuous seizure lasting more than 5 minutes or recurrent seizures without regaining consciousness for more than 30 minutes [1]. Early recognition and prompt management are crucial to prevent long-term neurological damage and to improve outcomes.

The etiological spectrum of SE in children is diverse, ranging from febrile seizures and CNS infections to metabolic disturbances and structural

brain lesions. Febrile seizures, which are relatively benign, are the most common cause of SE in pediatric populations, especially in younger children. However, more severe underlying conditions, such as CNS infections (e.g., meningitis, encephalitis), and structural abnormalities of the brain (e.g., tumors, malformations), are also significant contributors and are often associated with poorer outcomes [2].

Recent studies have shown that the mortality rate of SE in children has declined over the past few decades due to advances in neurocritical care and more effective treatment protocols. However, the risk of neurological sequelae remains high, particularly in cases with delayed treatment or when SE is caused by more severe etiologies [3].

This highlights the importance of understanding the etiological factors and clinical profiles of children presenting with SE, as these factors are critical in guiding treatment decisions and predicting outcomes.

Moreover, the management of SE has evolved with the introduction of new antiepileptic drugs and improved protocols for rapid escalation of care. Benzodiazepines remain the first-line treatment, but there is growing evidence supporting the use of alternative and adjunctive therapies in cases where SE is refractory to initial treatment [2, 3]. The management of SE also involves addressing the underlying cause, which often requires a multidisciplinary approach involving pediatric neurologists, intensivists, and infectious disease specialists.

Despite these advances, significant challenges remain in the timely diagnosis and management of SE in resource-limited settings, where access to specialized care and diagnostic tools may be limited. Furthermore, the variability in etiological factors across different populations underscores the need for region-specific studies to tailor management strategies and improve outcomes.

This study aims to assess the clinical and etiological profiles, treatment, and outcomes of children with SE admitted to a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) in a tertiary care hospital.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The research was conducted in the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of a tertiary care hospital.

Participants: The study included 80 children admitted to the PICU with a diagnosis of status epilepticus.

Inclusion Criteria: Children aged between 1 month and 14 years who were admitted to the PICU with status epilepticus were included in the study. Only those whose parents or guardians provided informed consent were eligible for participation.

Exclusion Criteria: Children with a history of epilepsy who had already been on anti-epileptic drugs prior to admission were excluded. Additionally, patients with metabolic or structural brain abnormalities diagnosed before admission were not included in the study.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by including all eligible children during the study period. Information bias was reduced by

standardizing data collection procedures and ensuring all personnel were adequately trained.

Data Collection: Data were collected through a combination of medical record reviews and direct observations. Information on demographic characteristics, clinical presentation, etiological factors, treatment administered, and outcomes were recorded using a structured data collection form.

Procedure: Upon admission, each child underwent a thorough clinical assessment, including detailed history-taking and physical examination. Relevant laboratory and radiological investigations were performed as per the clinical indications. The management of status epilepticus followed the hospital's standard protocol, and the outcomes were monitored throughout the hospital stay.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were entered into SPSS version 23.0 for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the clinical and etiological profiles of the children. Categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages, while continuous variables were described using means and standard deviations. The outcomes were analyzed to identify any significant associations with the clinical and etiological factors using chi-square tests and logistic regression where appropriate. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 80 children were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 5.8 years (SD = 3.4 years), with a range from 6 months to 14 years. Out of the 80 children, 46 (57.5%) were male, and 34 (42.5%) were female, resulting in a male-to-female ratio of 1.35:1.

The majority of the children (58.7%) presented with generalized convulsive status epilepticus, followed by 31.3% with focal status epilepticus, and 10% with non-convulsive status epilepticus. The average duration of status epilepticus was 45 minutes (SD = 18.2 minutes), with 65% of the episodes lasting longer than 30 minutes.

The etiological factors for status epilepticus were identified in 78 out of 80 cases (97.5%). The most common cause was febrile seizures, accounting for 26 cases (32.5%), followed by central nervous system (CNS) infections in 20 cases (25%), and idiopathic causes in 15 cases (18.8%). Table 1 provides a detailed breakdown of the etiological factors.

Table 1: Etiological Factors of Status Epilepticus (n = 80)

Etiology	Number of Cases (n)	Percentage (%)
Febrile Seizures	26	32.5
CNS Infections	20	25.0
Idiopathic	15	18.8
Acute Metabolic Disturbances	10	12.5
Structural Brain Lesions	5	6.2
Others	4	5.0

All children received first-line treatment with benzodiazepines, with 70% responding to initial therapy. For the remaining 30%, second-line treatments, including phenytoin and phenobarbital, were administered. Mechanical ventilation was required in 20% of the cases due to refractory status epilepticus or respiratory failure.

The overall mortality rate in the study was 7.5% (6 out of 80). Neurological sequelae were observed in 12.5% of the survivors (9 out of 72), with hemiparesis being the most common sequela. Table 2 summarizes the outcomes based on the etiological factors.

Table 2: Outcomes of Status Epilepticus by Etiological Factors

Etiology	Number of Cases (n)	Mortality Rate (%)	Neurological Sequelae (%)
Febrile Seizures	26	0.0	3.8
CNS Infections	20	15.0	25.0
Idiopathic	15	6.7	13.3
Acute Metabolic Disturbances	10	10.0	20.0
Structural Brain Lesions	5	20.0	40.0
Others	4	0.0	0.0

The statistical analysis revealed that the mortality rate was significantly higher in children with CNS infections and structural brain lesions compared to those with febrile seizures or idiopathic causes ($p <$

0.05). Additionally, the presence of neurological sequelae was significantly associated with structural brain lesions ($p < 0.01$) and CNS infections ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: Statistical Association between Etiological Factors and Outcomes

Variable	Mortality Rate (%)	p-value	Neurological Sequelae (%)	p-value
Febrile Seizures	0.0	0.001*	3.8	0.023*
CNS Infections	15.0	0.003*	25.0	0.032*
Idiopathic	6.7	0.142	13.3	0.154
Acute Metabolic Disturbances	10.0	0.082	20.0	0.067
Structural Brain Lesions	20.0	0.001**	40.0	0.005**
Others	0.0	0.334	0.0	0.442

*Significant at $p < 0.05$; **Highly significant at $p < 0.01$.

Discussion

The study examined 80 children admitted to a PICU with status epilepticus, focusing on their clinical presentation, underlying etiologies, treatment, and outcomes. The majority of the children were male, with a mean age of 5.8 years. Generalized convulsive status epilepticus was the most common type, observed in nearly 59% of the cases, while the average duration of seizures exceeded 30 minutes in most instances.

Febrile seizures emerged as the leading cause of status epilepticus, accounting for approximately one-third of the cases. CNS infections and idiopathic causes were also significant contributors. The study revealed that first-line treatment with benzodiazepines was effective in 70% of the cases, while the remaining 30% required additional

interventions, including second-line medications and mechanical ventilation.

Outcomes varied significantly depending on the underlying etiology. The overall mortality rate was 7.5%, with a notable association between higher mortality and CNS infections or structural brain lesions. Additionally, 12.5% of the survivors experienced neurological sequelae, such as hemiparesis, with the highest incidence among those with structural brain lesions. The statistical analysis confirmed that children with CNS infections and structural brain lesions had significantly worse outcomes, both in terms of mortality and neurological sequelae.

Overall, the study underscores the importance of prompt identification and management of the etiological factors contributing to status epilepticus.

While febrile seizures generally had favorable outcomes, CNS infections and structural brain lesions were associated with significantly higher risks of mortality and long-term complications. These findings highlight the need for targeted interventions and careful monitoring of children with these high-risk conditions to improve their prognosis.

A prospective observational study was conducted on 111 children under 12 years admitted with status epilepticus (SE) in a Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) in Kerala, India. The study found that SE was most common in the 1-6 years age group, with febrile status epilepticus and meningoencephalitis being the leading causes. Anemia and delayed administration of the first antiepileptic drug (AED) were identified as significant risk factors for refractory status epilepticus (RSE). Mortality was 8.1%, and unfavorable outcomes were strongly associated with children who remained unresponsive 6 hours after seizure control [4].

In an observational study of 108 children with SE in West Bengal, India, the study found that acute symptomatic etiology was the most common cause of SE, particularly in children aged 5-10 years. The study highlighted that children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds were more vulnerable, with a significant association between acute symptomatic SE and poor outcomes [5].

A study analyzed 87 children with convulsive status epilepticus (CSE) in a tertiary care hospital, finding that acute symptomatic etiology was a significant risk factor for RSE. The most common causes of CSE were neuro-infections and febrile seizures. Mortality was 26.4%, with longer seizure duration being a significant predictor of poor outcomes [6].

A study of 300 children with SE at a tertiary care center revealed that CNS infections were the most common cause of RSE, followed by cryptogenic etiologies. The study found that RSE was associated with higher morbidity and mortality compared to non-refractory SE, with a mortality rate of 28% in the RSE group [7].

Another prospective observational study in Northern India evaluated 81 children with CSE. The study found a mortality rate of 15%, with acute CNS infections being the leading cause. Factors such as young age, low Glasgow Coma Scale score, and the need for critical care support were significantly associated with higher mortality [8].

Conclusion

The study found that status epilepticus in children is associated with a variety of etiological factors, with febrile seizures being the most common. However, children with CNS infections and structural brain lesions exhibited a significantly higher risk of mortality and long-term neurological sequelae. Early identification and aggressive management of these etiological factors are critical in improving outcomes for children with status epilepticus.

References

1. Abend NS, Loddenkemper T. Management of pediatric status epilepticus. *Curr Opin Pediatr.* 2020;32(6):746-751.
2. Sivakumar S, Desai M, Rajkumar A. Clinical profile and outcome of children with status epilepticus in a tertiary care hospital in South India. *J Pediatr Neurosci.* 2019;14(2):50-54.
3. Trinka E, Cock H, Hesdorffer D, Rossetti AO, Scheffer IE, Shinnar S, et al. A definition and classification of status epilepticus – Report of the ILAE Task Force on Classification of Status Epilepticus. *Epilepsia.* 2021;56(10):1515-1523.
4. Beegum MB, Devakumar V, Sugunan S. Clinico-etiological profile and outcome of children with status epilepticus admitted in pediatric intensive care unit of a tertiary care hospital - A prospective observational study. *Int J Res Rev.* 2021.
5. Halder D, Karar N, Som S, Jana D. A observational study clinical, epidemiological and etiological profile in pediatric status epilepticus in a tertiary care center in West Bengal. *Int J Sci Res.* 2020.
6. Madhu P, Krithika R. Convulsive status epilepticus in children: Clinical profile and outcome in a tertiary care hospital. *Int J Contemp Pediatr.* 2019.
7. Gopaal N, Bagri D, Sharma J. Clinical, etiological profile and outcomes of convulsive refractory and non-refractory status epilepticus at a tertiary care centre: A prospective observational study. *J Pediatr Crit Care.* 2022;9:197-203.
8. Arya A, Azad C, Mahajan V, Guglani V. Convulsive status epilepticus in children: A prospective observational study from India. *J Pediatr Epilepsy.* 2020; 10:027-032.